

Examination of Some Vegetable Oils. Viscosities in Mixtures with Liquids of Low Viscosity

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Oils from seeds of *Pongamia glabra*, *P. mowrah* and *P. niger*, grown in Chotanagpur, Bihar, have been chemically examined. The characteristic values agree with previously published values showing that there is no significant seasonal or regional variation. The viscosities of the oils at 40° are 0.3238, 0.3185 and 0.2277 millipoises, respectively and energies of activation of viscous flow are about 8000 cal. mole⁻¹. Mixed with comparatively non-viscous liquids (kerosene, benzene and diesel), the corrected fluidities (*f*) of the oils are found to be proportional to volume available for flow (*v*). For any one vegetable oil, the plot of *f* against *v* does not change with change in the non-viscous solvent or temperature.

WE had earlier reported^{1,2} viscosities of some vegetable oils of Indian origin and their mixtures with solvents of low viscosity. The effect of temperature was also noted. The relation between viscosity coefficient (*η*) and % oil in non-viscous solvents (*c*) was found to be $\eta/c = \text{const} + \eta \cdot \text{const}$. We have examined three more oils (*karanj*, *mowrah* and *sarguja*) and found the same relations to be valid. We have further found that if *η* is corrected by subtraction of viscosity coefficient of the solvent, the graph for $\frac{\eta_{\text{cor}}}{C} = \text{const} + \eta_{\text{cor}} \cdot \text{const}$ for any one oil overlaps for all temperatures and nearly for all solvents. This is true for the oils previously reported^{1,2} as well as for the three oils reported here.

Experimental

The *Pongamia glabra* (*karanj*), *P. mowrah* (*mahua*) and *P. niger* (*sarguja*) oils were hand pressed from seeds collected in Chotanagpur. They were stored undisturbed for several days. The clear oils were decanted and used for chemical examinations and physical measurements.

The chemical analyses were carried out in the Public Health Laboratory at Patna. The results are shown in Table 1. The results may be compared with those given in the Wealth of India³ and by Jamieson⁴.

An examination of these data would characterize mahua oil as akin to olive oil, *karanj* oil as containing a single double-bond in the fatty acid moiety, while *sarguja* oil as containing two double bonds.

The physical measurements on the pure oils were carried out following the methods described earlier^{1,2}. The densities were determined with the help of a specific gravity bottle of ~20 ml capacity and are correct to four places. Ostwald viscometers with flow times of several minutes were used for viscosity measurements. The temperature was maintained constant to ±0.02°.

The results of physical measurements are shown in Table 2. It will be observed that successive decrements in *ρ* as well as *η* (for every 5° interval) slow down as the temperature increases except for some anomalous behaviour of mahua oil in respect

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

	Karanj		Mahua		Sarguja	
	Present investigation	Ref. 3	Present investigation	Ref. 4	Present investigation	Ref. 3
Acid value	4.3	6.3	10.6	—	5.08	2-11.7
Acetyl value	20.6	20.9	—	—	2.8	20-24
Iodine value	87.7	89.1	62.2	53-70	131	120-135
P. number	0.46	—	0.13	0.9	0.3	0.2
B. M. value	1.64	—	1.5	0.7-1.7	0.16	0.33-1.2
Sap. value	181	181	190	188-197	191	189-195
Thicy. value	—	—	—	—	84.6	85.5
Unsap. matter	4.1	4.2	1.3	0.8-3.5	0.8	0.3-3.65

TABLE 2—DATA OF PHYSICAL EXAMINATIONS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

		Temp. °C								
		20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
		Karanj oil								
I	—	—	—	1.4734	—	—	—	—	—	—
II	—	—	0.9298	0.9280	0.9262	0.9244	0.9227	0.9216	0.9205	0.9198
III	—	—	0.6554	0.5193	0.4049	0.8288	0.2637	0.2157	0.1797	0.1476
IV	—	—	—	—	26.47	—	—	—	—	—
V	—	—	0.0018	0.0018	0.0018	0.0017	0.0011	0.0011	0.0012	—
VI	—	—	0.1421	0.1084	0.0811	0.0601	0.0480	0.0360	0.0321	—
VII	—	—	0.2431	0.2361	0.2226	0.2011	0.2002	0.1821	0.1960	—
		Mahua oil								
I	—	—	—	—	—	1.4612	—	—	—	—
II	—	—	—	—	0.9068	0.9056	0.9044	0.9026	0.9010	0.8999
III	—	—	—	—	0.4008	0.8185	0.2586	0.2117	0.1754	0.1459
IV	—	—	—	—	27.24	—	—	—	—	—
V	—	—	—	—	0.0012	0.0012	0.0018	0.0011	0.0011	—
VI	—	—	—	—	0.0818	0.0599	0.0469	0.0363	0.0295	—
VII	—	—	—	—	0.2276	0.2076	0.1990	0.1875	0.1855	—
		Surguja oil								
I	—	—	—	—	—	1.4664	—	—	—	—
II	—	—	—	—	0.9180	0.9189	0.9121	0.9108	0.9097	0.9084
III	—	—	—	—	0.8428	0.2277	0.1898	0.1576	0.1332	0.1122
IV	—	—	—	—	29.41	—	—	—	—	—
V	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
VI	—	—	—	—	0.0017	0.0015	0.0020	0.0021	0.0018	0.0013
VII	—	—	—	—	0.1128	0.0830	0.0657	0.0494	0.0379	0.0322
	—	—	—	—	0.2389	0.2160	0.2119	0.1957	0.1815	0.1853
	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.0244	0.0210
	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.1678	0.1711

I—refractive index, II—density, III—viscosity coefficient, IV—surface tension, V— $\Delta\rho$, VI— $\Delta\eta$, VII— $\Delta\eta/\eta$

of ρ . Further $\frac{\Delta\eta}{\eta}$ dies out much more slowly than η . The surface tension values (dynes per cm) may be compared with that of castor oil (25.87; 35°). It appears that the OH group in ricinoleic acid has no particular effect in raising the surface tension though it raises the viscosity coefficient tremendously. Clearly therefore the hydroxyl group is in the bulk phase. We have also calculated the energies of activation of viscous flow from the plots of $\log \eta$ against $1/T$,

Oil	Castor	Acetyl castor	Karanj	Mahua	Sarguja	Argemone	Cesalpinia digyna
E_a cal./mole ⁻¹	13164	10001	8470	8222	7690	8336	8217

The E_a values (cal. mole⁻¹) are comparable to latent heats of vaporization for many organic liquids in the middle range of their melting points and critical temperatures⁹.

Viscosities of mixtures :

The viscosities of these oils in mixtures with comparatively non-viscous solvents namely benzene ($\eta=0.0049$ mp at 40°) and selected samples of kerosene ($\eta=0.0050$) and diesel ($\eta=0.0203$) have also been studied. These viscosities are of the order of 2 to 5% of the pure oils themselves at the same temperatures. The mixtures contained 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 90 and 100% of the pure oil by volume and measurements were made in the temperature range of 25-45° at 5° interval. The data are too extensive to be reported here in full. It was earlier^{1,2} found that plots of η/C against η at constant temperature

Fig. 1. ○ Karanj-benzene 30°, + Karanj-benzene 40°, × Karanj-kerosene 30°, △ Karanj-kerosene 40°, ⊙ Karanj-diesel 30°, ⊕ Karanj-diesel 40°.

gave straight lines. Our work on vapourization of liquids⁹ induced us to use corrected viscosities (i.e. observed viscosity of the mixture from which viscosity of the solvent is subtracted). The resulting $\frac{\eta_{cor}}{C}$ is still proportional to η_{cor} . It is now

observed that a change of solvent or temperature does not produce any substantial change in the graph for any one oil. Thus, in the case of karanj oil (Fig. 1), benzene and kerosene gave the same graph. The graph for diesel almost overlaps but a distinctly higher slope may be noticed. It was further found that our earlier data^{1,2} were also amenable to this finding.

The graphs in Fig. 1 correspond to the equation,

$$\frac{\eta_{abr}}{C} = \alpha\eta_{cor} + \beta \quad \dots (1)$$

Dividing (1) throughout by η_{cor} we find

$$\frac{1}{C} = \alpha + \frac{\beta}{\eta_{cor}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Now, $\frac{1}{C}$ is a measure of the volume occupied by the non-viscous liquid and $\frac{1}{\eta_{cor}}$ is a measure of corrected fluidity of the mixture. We may conclude that fluidity is proportional to volume occupied by the non-viscous component. It appears

that a small volume of non-viscous solvent added to these oils is sufficient to uncoil the large molecules fully and to remove all entanglements between them^{6,7}.

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